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Content

S.No.	Topic	Authors	Page No.
1	The Enablers and Inhibitors of Digital Transformation: Impacting Generation Z in Higher Education Institutions	Prof. Anil Khurana Ms. Neha	1-14
2	An Overview of Investor Sentiment: Uncovering Emerging Trends, Themes, and Future Directions via Bibliometric Analysis	Dr. Satpal Ms. Reetu	15-27
3	Assessing Challenges in Rural Development and Water Sustainability: A Socioeconomic Viewpoint on Groundwater Management and Integrated Governance Solutions in India	Mr. Aniket Sachan	28-37
4	Analyzing the Role of Skill India in Bilateral Trade between India and China and its Impact on India's Gross Domestic Product	Dr. Vivek Singh Ms. Sonali Yadav	38-45
5	Empirically Analyzing the Impact of Remittances on the REER: An Indian Context	Prof. Rachna Mujoo Ms. Sanjana Prakash	46-56
6	An Empirical Analysis of Remittance Flow in India	Mr. Shivam Agarwal Prof. Rachna Mujoon	57-64
7	Role of Prime Minister Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP) in Promoting Entrepreneurship and Employment: A Study of Bihar	Dr Vivek Singh Ms. Neha Dubey	65-74
8	Multiclass Classification of Coronavirus (COVID-19) using Grey Wolf Optimization and Transfer Learning-based Ensemble Model	Mr. Abhishek Agnihotri Prof. Narendra Kohli	75-83

Analyzing the Role of Skill India in Bilateral Trade between India and China and its Impact on India's Gross Domestic Product

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ABSTRACT

Skill India aims to empower the country's workforce by providing training and education to enhance employability and promote entrepreneurship. The study analyses the impact of India's exports and imports from China on India's gross domestic product after the skill India initiative. The International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Bank, World Trade Organization (WTO), Reserve Bank of India (RBI), and the Ministry of Commerce and Industry etc. have contributed to the compilation of all data. In this study, Excel was utilized to perform tests for correlation, regression analysis, and analysis of variance (ANOVA). Analysing the data reveals that the correlation between India's exports to China and gross domestic product reveals a very highly positive relationship indicated by the correlation coefficient of 0.90507827. The value of R^2 is 0.819166675, which suggests that approximately 81.91% of the variability in gross domestic product can be explained by the variations in India's exports to China. The value of F is 22.64977092 which is statistically significant with a value of significance F is 0.005063123 which indicates a significant impact of India's exports to China on the gross domestic product after the skill India initiative. The correlation between India's imports from China and gross domestic product is moderately positive with a correlation coefficient of 0.7296743. The value of R Square is 0.532424584 which indicates that approximately 53.24% of the variability in gross domestic product can be explained by the variations in India's imports from China. The value of F is 5.693462112 which is statistically significant with a value of significance F of 0.062689776 which indicates no significant impact of India's imports from China on the gross domestic product after the skill India initiative.

In conclusion, the skill India initiative has improved the relationship between India's exports to China and its gross domestic product. The skills gained from this initiative have boosted India's economy, especially in terms of exports to China. Skill India has shown no significant impact on the relationship between imports from China and India's gross domestic product. This indicates that the skills learned through Skill India do not have any impact on the relationship between India's imports to China and India's economic growth.

Keywords: India-China, Bilateral trade, Skill India, Gross Domestic Product

INTRODUCTION

Skill India was launched in 2015 to develop India's workforce by training young people in specialized skills such as plumbing, electrical work, manufacturing, medical care, and information technology programming. The initiative seeks to capitalize on its youth's statistical advantages while simultaneously fostering socioeconomic success. Skill India also seeks to enhance collaborations with businesses to better integrate training programs with industry demands, ensuring that the skills acquired contribute to the job market and give opportunities for interested individuals. Skill India was initiated by the Indian government as a program to provide Indian youngsters with industry-relevant skills to promote economic growth. As India's population enters the demographic dividend era, the government wants to close the skills gap and meet the sector's needs. Skill India strives to provide adolescents with the skills needed to find suitable professions or establish their businesses. The project intends

to skill, reskill, and upgrade India's workforce to meet changing demands, ensuring that they have good lives and contribute to the country's prosperity. The project seeks to close the skills gap in the workforce and meet the needs of various industries, ensuring that adolescents are prepared for acceptable jobs and entrepreneurial enterprises. The effort intends to help India's economic goals by cultivating a competent workforce outside of conventional sectors, with an emphasis on technology, healthcare, and renewable energy. It aspires to keep India competitive in a fast-changing global marketplace by equipping people with updated skills. The initiative intends to provide the country's workers with the necessary skills and capacities to adapt to future employment positions and technology, assuring India's sustained success in the global economy.

In conclusion, Skills India plays a critical role in India's economic progress by catalyzing and unleashing the potential of its young labour. With its holistic approach, this plan aims to develop a competent and dynamic workforce capable of promoting innovation, entrepreneurship, and long-term economic growth, ultimately establishing India as a strong player in the world economy.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Jameel Ahmed (2021) in their paper explores the potential for Skill India's development and job generation. Skill India's primary purpose is to raise confidence, increase output, and give guidance through effective skill development. Skill India will create blue-collar jobs for the youth. According to this study, employability improved from 33.95% in 2014 to 45.6% in 2018, demonstrating the government's outstanding performance. This demonstrates how important skill development is to a country's prosperity and growth.¹

Dr. Rajni Arora and Manoj Chhadwani (2019) evaluated the influence of Skill India on transforming the Indian economy, emphasizing the importance of the Skill India Campaign. The Skill India initiatives are implemented as part of the government's effort to boost the economy. This study concludes that while the government has built a regulatory framework, the sector should also participate in a public private partnership to increase skills.²

Gawade Santosh Bhiwa examines that Knowledge, skill, and technology are the backbone of the economy. A skill development process should also be implemented along with education to improve the quality of education.³

Dr. Ranjit Kumar Elamadurthi, Dr. R S Varahala Dora, Dr. Chitti Babu Putcha and Dr. Ramana Yadla (2023) examine the importance of skill development initiatives in India's poverty-reduction efforts. It employs literary references and empirical studies to examine many elements of these projects, including their influence on poverty reduction and the obstacles they encounter. The essay presents a detailed knowledge of how skill development might help India become wealthier and more egalitarian. It also highlights government policies and programs to assist communities in emerging from poverty.⁴

Dr. Deepa Gupta and Sugandha Agarwal (2018) examine the extant literature on skill development in India, with an emphasis on government efforts, public-private partnerships, and methods for increasing employable skills. It examines the obstacles encountered in these programs, addresses the skills taught through educational programs, the rapid learning age group, and the need for further sector-specific courses. The goal is to identify the requirements, problems, and extent of skill development initiatives in India.⁵

Sonali Kanchan and Sakshi Varshney (2015) analysed that skill development is an important aspect of promoting macroeconomic growth and social stability. India has set lofty targets for quicker and more sustainable economic growth, emphasizing the need to equip its workers with necessary skills. As a national priority, different steps have been implemented to address the issue. This study examines the present state of skill development in India, as well as the problems associated with executing various programs and plans.⁶

Radhika Kapur (2014) emphasized the role of skill development in India, as well as the numerous measures and policies to encourage it. India has progressively become a more conscientious nation due to its profusion of highly qualified, informed, and experienced human resources. Literacy, reading, writing, computer skills, artisan skills and manufacturing have all been taught in training facilities in both urban and rural communities.⁷

Ankul Pandey and Dr. D K Nema (2017) in their paper analysed that Indian youth face unemployment due to a lack of technical knowledge, despite being educated. The country's skills development system faces obstacles in training the youth, as most are unaware of modern technology.⁸

Vandana Saini (2015) explores India's skill capability and the issues associated with skill development projects. It demonstrates that 38% of the Indian workforce aged 15 to 59 is illiterate, 25% has less than elementary education, 36% has medium and higher education, and just 10% is vocationally skilled.⁹

Lavina Sharma And Asha Nagendra (2016) examined that the youngest workforce country globally, has the lowest median age, making it the largest provider of workforce. However, the country is having difficulties to fill the jobs due to a lack of qualified applicants. This also has an impact on matching jobs to available talents. In terms of skill transfer, India lags behind nations such as China and Singapore.¹⁰

Anita Swain and Sunita Swain (2020) in their paper examined the various challenges faced by our country's youth, as well as the schemes particularly the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) and the Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDU-GKY), implemented by government to address such challenges. In this paper they have analyzed that there is a tremendous opportunity to create a skilled workforce and take advantage of “demographic dividend” and also branding initiatives and active participation of public-private partnerships to enable the greater supply of skilled workforce.¹¹

Mishil Trivedi (2023) examines the Skill India Mission's influence on the national economy and people. It examines various government efforts within the mission's scope, with an emphasis on their economic and skill development implications. The study examines the program's success and degree of achievement, concluding that it was moderately successful. The goal of the study is to examine if the Skill India Mission has had a substantial influence on the nation's economy.¹²

RESEARCH GAP

After reviewing the research paper, it was found that researchers conducted the studies on the impact of skill India initiative in various aspects. Some researchers have looked at the impact of Skill India on job creation while others have looked at the impact of Skill India on the Indian economy. Researchers have found that due to Skill India implementation, tremendous opportunities are being created for skilled workers. In the paper, we studied the impact of India's exports and imports from China on Gross Domestic Product after the Skill India initiative.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study on the role of Skill India in bilateral trade between India and China holds significant importance in understanding the dynamics of economic collaboration between these two nations. The research aims to identify potential impacts on India's gross domestic product by analyzing the impact of the Skill India initiative on the workforce and its subsequent impact on bilateral trade. This investigation is crucial for policymakers and stakeholders, providing insights that can guide strategic decisions to enhance economic cooperation, address skill gaps and optimize the positive impact of such collaborations on India's overall economic growth.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To provide an overview of bilateral trade between India and China from 2015-2016 to 2021-2022.
2. To examine the impact of India's exports to China on gross domestic product after the Skill India initiative.
3. To examine the impact of India's imports from China on gross domestic product after the Skill India initiative.

HYPOTHESIS OF STUDY

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of India's exports to China on gross domestic product after the Skill India initiative.

H₁₁: There is a significant impact of India's exports to China on gross domestic product after the Skill India initiative.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of India's imports from China on gross domestic product after the Skill India initiative.

H₁₂: There is a significant impact of India's imports from China on gross domestic product after the Skill India initiative.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study aimed to analyze the role of Skill India in bilateral trade between India and China and its impact on India's gross domestic product. This research is based on secondary data sources. In the study, data have been collected from the International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Bank, World Trade Organization (WTO), Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Ministry of Commerce and Industry etc. between the time-frame of 2015-2022. In the research, MS Excel is used for the calculation and correlation, regression analysis and Anova have been used to examine the impact of imports and exports to China on India's gross domestic product after the Skill India initiative.

Table 1: Variables used in the study (amount in US \$ BILLION)

YEAR	EXPORTS TO CHINA	IMPORTS FROM CHINA	GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT
2015-2016	9.01	61.7	2290
2016-2017	10.17	61.28	2650
2017-2018	13.33	76.38	2700
2018-2019	16.75	70.31	2840
2019-2020	16.61	65.26	2670
2020-2021	21.18	65.21	3150
2021-2022	21.25	94.57	3420

Source: Ministry of Commerce and Industry, World Bank Database

OVERVIEW OF INDIA AND CHINA BILATERAL TRADE FROM 2015-2016 TO 2021-2022

Figure 1: India's exports and imports from China from 2015-2016 to 2021-2022

Source: Ministry of Commerce and Industry

India and China are two largest and fastest-growing economies in world. Bilateral trade between these countries has been growing rapidly over the past few years, but the relationship between the two countries has been marked by tensions, particularly in the political and military spheres. Here is an overview of India and China's bilateral trade from 2015-2016 to 2021-2022:

Trade Volume - In 2015-2016, the total bilateral trade between India and China was US \$ 70.71 billion. In 2019-2020, this figure had risen to US \$ 81.87 billion. However, in 2020-2021, total bilateral trade reached US \$ 86.39 billion and in 2021-2022, the total trade volume further increased to US \$ 115.82 billion.

Trade Balance - India has had a significant trade imbalance with China in recent years. In 2015-2016, India's imports from China totaled US \$ 61.70 billion, while its exports to China were just US \$ 9.01 billion. This trade deficit has grown over time, and in 2019-2020, India's imports from China were worth US \$ 65.26 billion, while its exports to China were just US \$ 16.61 billion. In 2021-2022, India's imports from China were worth US\$ 94.57 billion, while its exports to China were worth US \$ 21.25 billion.

Tensions And Restrictions - The bilateral trade relationship between India and China has been marked by tensions and restrictions. In 2020, India imposed restrictions on the import of certain Chinese goods, to reduce its dependence on Chinese imports and China also imposed restrictions on Indian products.

Table 2: Correlation result of India's exports to China and Gross Domestic Product

	EXPORTS TO CHINA	GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT
EXPORTS TO CHINA	1	0.90507827
GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT	0.90507827	1

Source: Excel output

Table 3: Regression result of India’s exports to China and Gross Domestic Product

REGRESSION STATISTICS	
Multiple R	0.90507827
R Square	0.819166675
Adjusted R Square	0.78300001
Standard Error	171.7845509
Observations	7

Independent Variable: Exports to China

Dependent Variable: Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Annual)

Source: Excel output

Table 4: Anova result of India’s exports to China and Gross Domestic Product

ANOVA					
	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	668393.1976	668393.1976	22.64977092	0.005063123
Residual	5	147549.6596	29509.93191		
Total	6	815942.8571			

Source: Excel output

INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF INDIA’S EXPORTS TO CHINA ON GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT AFTER THE SKILL INDIA INITIATIVE

The correlation analysis between India's exports to China and gross domestic product reveals a very highly positive relationship, with a correlation coefficient of 0.90507827. This indicates a high degree of correlation between the two variables which indicates that as India's exports to China increase there is a corresponding rise in the gross domestic product. The coefficient of determination is 0.819166675 explaining approximately 81.91 % of the variance in gross domestic product based on the variations in exports to China. The Adjusted R Square is 0.78300001 which implies that the model's explanatory power remains robust even after considering potential confounding factors. The F-statistic, with a value of 22.64977092, tests the overall significance of the regression model. The Significance F value of 0.005063123 is below the significance threshold of 0.05, indicating that the model is statistically significant. This suggests that India’s exports to China have a significant impact on the gross domestic product.

Table 5: Correlation result of India’s Imports from China and Gross Domestic Product

	IMPORTS FROM CHINA	GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT
IMPORTS FROM CHINA	1	0.7296743
GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT	0.7296743	1

Source: Excel output

Table 6: Regression result of India’s Imports from China and Gross Domestic Product

REGRESSION STATISTICS	
Multiple R	0.7296743
R Square	0.532424584
Adjusted R Square	0.4389095
Standard Error	276.2299119
Observations	7

Independent Variable: Imports from China

Dependent Variable: Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Annual)

Source: Excel output

Table 7: Anova result of India’s Imports from China and Gross Domestic Product

ANOVA					
	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	434428.0359	434428.0359	5.693462112	0.062689776
Residual	5	381514.8212	76302.96424		
Total	6	815942.8571			

Source: Excel output

INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF INDIA’S IMPORTS FROM CHINA ON GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT AFTER THE SKILL INDIA INITIATIVE

The correlation analysis between India's imports from China and gross domestic product reveals a moderate positive relationship with correlation coefficient of 0.7296743. This indicates a moderate degree of correlation between the two variables, suggesting that as India's imports to China increase, there is a corresponding rise in the gross domestic product. The R square is 0.532424584 explaining approximately 53.24 % of the variance in Gross Domestic Product based on the variations in imports to China. The Adjusted R Square is 0.4389095 which implies that the model's explanatory power remains robust even after considering potential confounding factors. The F-statistic, with a value of 5.693462112, tests the overall significance of the regression model. The Significance F value of 0.062689776 is more than the significance threshold of 0.05 which indicates that India’s imports from China have no significant impact on gross domestic product.

CONCLUSION

This paper has tried to analyze the impact of India's exports and imports from China on gross domestic product after the Skill India initiative. The statistical analysis highlights a strong and positive relationship between India's exports to China and its gross domestic product, with a substantial portion of the variability in gross domestic product explained by variations in exports. The statistical significance F value indicates that India's exports to China have a significant impact on its gross domestic product after the Skill India initiative. The correlation between India's imports from China and gross domestic product is moderately positive. While there is a statistically significant relationship, the explanatory power of variations in imports on gross domestic product is moderate. The statistical significance F value indicates that India's imports from China may not have a significant impact on its gross domestic product after the Skill India initiative.

The Skill India project is helping to boost India's economic position in China. By focusing on talent development, this effort has become a cornerstone in improving the link between exports and gross domestic product. The trained workforce generated by Skill India not only helps to increase productivity but also allows for adaptive responses to the changing needs of the global market. The initiative's emphasis on skill development trains individuals to thrive in industries important to India's exports to China. This involves enhancing product quality, using cutting-edge technology, and enabling better communication and engagement. The strategic partnership with Skill India guarantees that the Indian workforce stays inventive and capable of dealing with the difficulties of global commerce. This increases and broadens India's economic presence in the Chinese market.

Skill India emerges as a revolutionary force in determining economic dynamics. A competent staff is acknowledged as a valuable asset for fostering innovation, improving efficiency, and increasing global competitiveness. Skill India strives to reduce India's dependency on Chinese imports by boosting indigenous companies and improving manufacturing capabilities.

The significant influence of Skill India is seen in the empowerment of the workers to engage in value-added activities, which benefits the manufacturing process. Skill India helps long-term economic growth by boosting the native workforce and industry, lessening India's reliance on external variables such as Chinese imports.

In conclusion, the Skill India Initiative emerges as a crucial driver in increasing India's exports to China by building a highly trained workforce. This trained labour force, capable of fulfilling global market needs, is critical to increasing India's exports to China. Furthermore, Skill India contributes significantly to reducing reliance on Chinese imports by boosting domestic firms and expanding manufacturing capabilities. This initiative's larger impact extends beyond immediate economic concerns, contributing to long-term prosperity and building a robust, self-sufficient economic environment for India in the face of complicated global trade dynamics.

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